

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON/MODIFIED BISMALIMIDE COMPOSITES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY: The fracture toughness K_{Ic} , interlaminar shear strength τ_{ILSS} and tensile strength σ_t of composites of carbon fiber T300 reinforced modified bismaleimide QY8911 (T300/MBMI) have been investigated in the temperature range 20-200°C. These are compared with the corresponding results for carbon fiber composites with epoxy matrix (T300/EP). In-situ observation of the above experiments in the scanning electron microscope has provided indications of important characteristics of dynamic crack propagation and delamination development. T300/MBMI composites are found to have higher K_{Ic} , τ_{ILSS} , and σ_t than the epoxy based composites. In general, the MBMI composites show a higher temperature resistance and lower crack and delamination propagation rates, and are thus superior to the epoxy based composites. This is so because of the greater thermal stability and toughness and better interfacial adhesion in the modified BMI matrix material. The failure mechanisms of the composites are investigated by analyses of SEM fractographs. Of the three mechanical properties studied, interlaminar shear strength is most affected by temperature.

KEYWORDS: carbon fiber reinforced modified bismaleimide composites, mechanical behaviour, fracture toughness, interlaminar shear, microstructure, elevated temperature

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites, as a class of high performance materials, finds major use in structural applications. Very often, a judicious choice of the matrix material can enable special requirements to be met in particular applications. Epoxy resins are most popularly used in high performance fiber composites. Disadvantages of epoxy-based composites, however, include low fracture toughness, low delamination resistance and poor performance in a hot/wet environment. These reflect the inherent brittleness and low thermal resistance of the epoxies. Compared to the epoxies, bismaleimide (BMI) resins exhibit better thermal as well as humidity resistance, and are thus more suited to be used in demanding environments. BMIs are, however, brittle and difficult to process [1], and various chemical and physical modifications are the subject of active investigation.

This work makes use of a modified bismaleimide resin, QY8911 (MBMI-1), reported in [2]. This MBMI-1 resin has good processability and possesses better toughness than BMI while retaining the original advantages in thermal stability. We have previously investigated the impact resistance [3] and the fracture fatigue [4] as well as the interlaminar fracture [5] behaviour of carbon fiber reinforced MBMI-1 composites (CF/MBMI-1) under room temperature conditions.

In the present work, the fracture toughness, interlaminar shear strength and tensile strength of CF/MBMI-1 composites are evaluated at elevated temperatures and comparison of performance with epoxy-based CF composites is made. To gain an understanding of the thermal fracture and delamination processes, experiments have also been performed in a scanning electron microscope with in-situ heating and loading capabilities. We aim to provide an evaluation of the thermal resistance as well as to elucidate the high temperature failure mechanisms in CF/MBMI-1 composites.

SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The specimens were made from T300 carbon fiber with modified bismaleimide QY8911 (T300/MBMI-1) and epoxy EP618 (T300/EP) matrices. The MBMI-1 resin was prepared by incorporating a dispersion of thermoplastic PES particles in BMI resin [2]. The elongation at break of MBMI-1 (2.2%) matches that of T300 carbon fiber. The tensile strength and modulus of MBMI-1 are 66 MPa and 3.5 GPa, respectively, and are higher than the corresponding epoxy values. The fiber volume fraction in the composites was approximately 65%; [0] and [± 45] lay-ups were prepared from unidirectional prepregs of thickness 0.11 mm. The quality of the laminates was examined by the ultrasonic C-scan technique before test. Specimen dimensions conformed with ASTM D3039-76 for test of tensile strength, ASTM D2234-84 for interlaminar shear strength and ASTM E399 for fracture toughness. Testing was performed on an Instron 1175 machine with an auxiliary high temperature oven. Fracture and short beam shear tests were also carried out on a Cambridge S-250 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with in-situ heating and loading capabilities. For SEM study, specimen dimensions were reduced in proportion to the ASTM size. The damage process and dynamic crack propagation could be observed and photographed in the SEM loading stage. Experiments in this study were performed at room temperature 20°C as well as at elevated temperatures (150 and 200°C).

COMPARISON OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED MODIFIED BISMALEIMIDE AND EPOXY COMPOSITES

The fracture toughness K_{Ic} , interlaminar shear strength τ_{ILSS} and tensile strength σ_t of T300/MBMI-1 [0] (U-B), T300/MBMI-1 [± 45] (M-B), T300/Epoxy [0] (U-E) and T300/EP [± 45] (M-E) specimens at various temperatures are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of mechanical properties of carbon fiber T300 reinforced MBMI-1 and EP618 composites at elevated temperatures

Specimen Type	Symbol	T °C	Tensile Strength		Interlaminar Shear		Fracture Toughness	
			σ_t (MPa)	R(%)	τ_{ILSS} (MPa)	R(%)	K_{Ic} (MPa \sqrt{m})	R(%)
T300/MBMI-1 [0]	U-B	20	1327	100	90.1	100	46.4	100
		150	1163	88	54.7	61	41.6	90
		200	617	47	26.1	29	27.8	60
T300/EP618 [0]	U-E	20	1275	100	72.8	100	30.6	100
		150	1049	71	12.4	17	18.0	59
		200	470	37	7.3	10	15.3	50
T300/MBMI-1 [±45]	M-B	20	102	100	28.6	100	26.4	100
		150	72	71	4.9	17	5.1	19
		200	35	34	2.6	9	2.8	11
T300/EP618 [±45]	M-E	20	94	100	26.3	100	19.7	100
		150	52	56	2.3	9	2.4	12
		200	20	21	1.5	6	1.8	9

R-Retention Rate, MBMI-1 - Modified BMI Resin, EP618 - Epoxy Resin

Fracture Toughness

The room temperature fracture toughness K_{Ic} value of U-B (resp. M-B) is 46.4 MPa \sqrt{m} (26.4 MPa \sqrt{m}), and is 52% (34%) higher than that of U-E (resp. M-E). At 150°C, the retention rate R of K_{Ic} in U-B (resp. M-B) is 90% (19%) and is 31% (7%) better than in U-E (resp. M-E). At 200°C, although the R values of the MBMI-1 and EP composites are comparable, the K_{Ic} value of U-B (resp. M-B) is 82% (56%) larger than that of U-E (resp. M-E). The [0] composites are seen to be much less affected by temperature than the [±45] composites. MBMI-1 composites in either lay-up have greater fracture toughness than in the corresponding EP composites at all temperatures investigated. This is attributed to the greater toughness of MBMI-1 at room temperature and at elevated temperatures.

Interlaminar Shear Strength

The room temperature τ_{ILSS} value of U-B (resp. M-B) is 90.1 MPa (28.6 MPa) and is 24% (9%) higher than that of U-E (resp. M-E). At 150°C, the R value in U-B (M-B) is 61% (17%) and is 44% (8%) better than that in U-E (resp. M-E). At 200°C, the τ_{ILSS} value of U-B (resp. M-B) is 258% (73%) larger than that of U-E (resp. M-E). Again, the [0] composites are less affected by temperature than the [±45] composites. MBMI-1 composites in either lay-up have greater τ_{ILSS} than in the corresponding EP composites at all temperatures investigated because MBMI-1 has better interfacial adhesion properties. Deterioration in τ_{ILSS} in the [0] composites at elevated temperatures is much more marked than in the case of fracture toughness or tensile strength, and is therefore a sensitive performance indicator for the evaluation of a new matrix material.

Tensile Strength

The room temperature σ_t value of U-B (resp. M-B) is 1327 MPa (102 MPa) and is a little higher than that of U-E (resp. M-E). At 150°C, the R value in U-B (resp. M-B) is 88% (71%) and is 17% (15%) better than that in U-E (resp. M-E). At 200°C, the σ_t value of U-B (resp. M-B) is 31% (75%) larger than that of U-E (resp. M-E). In the [0] composites, σ_t is mainly determined by the fiber performance, thus σ_t differences between MBMI-1 and EP composites are minimal; the matrix contribution is seen to become more apparent in [± 45] composites, with those based on MBMI-1 giving higher retention rates.

From the above experimental results, it is clear that the fracture toughness, interlaminar shear strength and tensile strength of T300/MBMI-1 composites are uniformly better than those of T300/EP, at room temperature as well as at elevated temperatures.

IN-SITU SEM OBSERVATION OF FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TEST

Single edge notched specimens with notch length to specimen width of 0.3 were subjected to three point bending fracture test in the SEM. Micrographs of the damage zone at the notch tip were taken during test. The fracture process followed the three stages : (1) initial cracking at notch tip, (2) crack propagation and development of damage, (3) failure and fracture.

For M-B (resp. M-E) at 150°C, cracks started to occur at the notch tip when the load level reached 60% (29%) of fracture load P_f , and propagated along the 45° interface direction with further load increase (Fig. 1) (resp. Fig. 2). Sudden failure occurred at 98% P_f (73% P_f) level. At this point, M-E failed by brittle fracture while with M-B more 45° cracks began to develop and complete fracture (Fig. 3) came at a slightly higher load. Comparing initial cracks, M-E also showed brittle cracking (Fig. 4), reflecting a break down of epoxy at the notch tip at 150°C. Overall, damage in M-B is much less extensive than in M-E, indicating MBMI-1 has a better thermal resistance than EP, and hence a higher fracture toughness for M-B.

For U-E at 200°C (150°C), the notch tip opened (Fig. 5) at 25% P_f (32% P_f) and started to propagate along the 0° interface direction at 30% P_f (49% P_f), resulting in more than one slip line (Fig. 6). The phenomenon of multiple slip lines does not normally occur in room temperature testing, and hence its occurrence suggests the thermal cracking of the epoxy matrix. For U-B, notch opening occurred at higher load levels, but U-B and U-E failed in similar ways.

IN-SITU SEM OBSERVATION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH TEST

Short beam shear tests were performed in the SEM. For U-B (resp. U-E) at 200°C, noticeable deformation occurred at 67% (27%) of the maximum load P_{max} , then shear delamination at 89% P_{max} (63% P_{max}). Beyond P_{max} , the load recovered after a slight decrease, followed by a succession of drops as interlaminar layers gave way. Fig. 7a (resp. Fig. 7b) shows the delamination failure of U-B (resp. U-E). Shear delamination in U-B is less serious than in U-E. Interface debonding as observed in between the outermost plies and matrix damage in U-B (Fig. 8) are not as severe as in U-E (Fig. 9) where the epoxy is smashed with broken fibers visible. The latter phenomenon does not occur in room temperature testing. For [± 45] composites, failure also occurred via shear cracking at roughly 45° through the thickness of a

ply connecting adjacent delaminated interlaminar layers (Fig. 10). This is a result of the interface debonding of 45° plies which will not appear in [0] composites, manifesting in more noticeable thermal degradation of [±45] composites compared to [0] composites.

Fig. 1: Cracks propagate along interface direction in T300/MBMI [±45] specimen (150°C)

Fig. 2: Brittle cracking along 45° interface direction in T300/EP [±45] specimen (150°C)

Fig. 3: Brittle fracture of T300/EP [±45] specimen (150°C)

Fig. 4: Enhanced thermal resistance in T300/MBMI [±45] specimen (150°C)

Fig. 5: Notch opening and cracking in T300/EP [0] specimen (200°C)

Fig. 6: Cracks propagate along 0° interface direction in T300/EP [0] specimen (200°C); more than one slip line is visible

(a) *T300/MBMI [0]* (b) *T300/EP [0]*
Fig. 7: Interlaminar shear failure at 200°C

Fig. 8: Debonding in *T300/MBMI [0]* specimen (200°C)

Fig. 9: Debonded matrix and broken fiber in *T300/EP [0]* specimen

Fig. 10: 45° shear cracking through ply thickness in *T300/MBMI [±45]* specimen (150°C)

Fig. 11: Shear yielding in MBMI matrix at 200°C

Fig. 12: Thermal cracking and decomposition of epoxy matrix (200°C)

RESIN DEGRADATION AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

Higher crosslink density and stiffer molecular chains contribute to the stronger interfacial adhesion in MBMI-1. At 200°C, the epoxy resin will experience thermal cracking as well as chemical decomposition, while MBMI-1 can still maintain good thermo-oxidative stability. Major decomposition of MBMI-1 resin occurs at approximately 390°C with glass transition at 257°C, which are higher than epoxy's 200°C and 150°C, respectively. Moreover, MBMI-1 is toughened by PES particles, with a high fracture work of 2381 N-m. Its elongation at break is 2.2%, which is 46% higher than epoxy's 1.5%, matching that of T300. All these contribute to an adequate fiber-matrix adhesion and to the occurrence of shear yielding in MBMI-1 composites even at elevated temperatures (Fig. 11). In epoxy composites at high temperatures, however, interface debonding as well as matrix cracking and decomposition often occur (Fig. 12).

CONCLUSION

- (1) As a result of the good thermal resistance and thermal stability of MBMI-1, there is a high retention rate of mechanical properties, especially fracture toughness, in T300/MBMI-1 composites at elevated temperatures. In particular, the unidirectional MBMI-1 composites seem to be capable of working in 150°C service environments under all loading conditions investigated here, and perhaps also in 200°C environments to a limited extent. In all cases tested, MBMI-1 composites have a notable advantage over EP composites at 150°C.
- (2) The PES-toughened MBMI-1 resin gives MBMI-1 [0] and MBMI-1 [± 45] composites 52% and 34% more fracture toughness than that found in EP [0] and EP [± 45] composites, respectively. The good room-temperature toughness of MBMI-1 composites also offers potential for practical applications.
- (3) The thermal fracture mechanisms and failure processes of the carbon fiber MBMI-1 and EP composites have been characterized by in-situ observation of tests performed in the SEM. In MBMI-1 composites, delamination as well as notch tip blunting and cracking are delayed by the toughened matrix, especially at elevated temperatures. Interfacial adhesion and bonding tend to be less affected by temperature. However, in EP composites, the brittle nature and the lower thermal resistance of epoxy lead to earlier occurrence of initial cracking, faster crack propagation rates and more serious delamination. At elevated temperatures, cracks propagate along the fiber direction as is the case at room temperature. There are, however, more slip lines in the thermal environment. In both MBMI-1 and EP composites, interlaminar cracking through the ply thickness also occur in [± 45] composites, resulting in more serious thermal degradation than in [0] composites. The thermal degradation in interlaminar shear strength is more marked than in fracture toughness or tensile strength; this is because the effect of debonding has less influence on tension and fracture. Important thermal degradation mechanisms for the carbon fiber composites studied include matrix cracking, interface debonding and matrix decomposition, the latter being a limiting factor for the performance of EP composites at 200°C.
- (4) Our results indicate that MBMI-1 has high temperature resistance and good toughness and MBMI-1 based carbon fiber composites can retain a useful fraction of room

temperature mechanical performance when tested at elevated temperatures. It appears that these composites are suitable for use at service temperatures of up to 150°C. Together with the good processability of the MBMI-1 resin, there is a substantial potential for MBMI-1 composites to find a variety of applications.

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REFERENCES

1. Byung, H., Lee, M., Ashraf, C. and Yefin, B., "Recent Development of High Performance Bismaleimide Resins", *Polymer News*, Vol. 13, 1988, pp. 297-301.
2. Zhao, Q.S., Li, Y.H., Cao, Z.H. and Sun, D.S., "New Modified Bismaleimide Resin for Graphite Composites", *Proc. of SAMPE 34th*, 1989, pp. 27-32.
3. Xian, X.J. and Choy, C.L., "Impact Resistance and Damage Evaluation of Carbon Reinforced Modified Bismaleimide Composites", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 13, December 1994, pp. 1135-1153.
4. Xian, X.J. and Choy, C.L., "Fatigue Fracture Behaviour of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Modified Bismaleimide Composites", *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 52, 1995, pp. 93-98.
5. Xian, X.J. and Choy, C.L., "The Interlaminar Fracture Behaviour and Toughening Mechanism of New Carbon Fiber Reinforced Bismaleimide Composites", *Composites*, Vol. 26, No. 1, 1995, pp. 33-39.